

Acidified dough processing of faba bean protein concentrates: A pathway to enhanced ingredient functionality

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ABSTRACT

The application of lactic acid fermentation to improve the nutritional, functional and sensory properties of plant protein ingredients is gaining considerable interest. In this study, we hypothesised that dough formation and acidification by addition of lactic acid per se can modify the techno-functional properties of faba bean protein concentrate (FPC). FPC was formed into a dough, acidified using lactic acid and incubated at 37 °C for 18 h to mimic conditions during lactic acid fermentation. Texture analysis revealed a higher hardness for the acidified dough of 421.1 ± 8.4 g compared to 106.3 ± 8.6 g for the non-acidified dough. Results showed a more open and disrupted protein network of the acidified dough, shifts in protein secondary structure, and differences in structural domains, with the acidified dough exhibiting a population of tightly bound protons of 87.5 % ± 1.6 % compared to 22.0 % ± 3.2 % for the non-acidified dough. Dispersing the doughs in water (5 % w/w protein) and adjusting the pH to 4.4, 6.4 or 7.0 enabled screening of their techno-functional properties. Similar protein solubilities of the dispersions were found at pH 4.4 (9.7 ± 0.3–10.6 ± 0.3 %). At pH 7.0, however, both the non-acidified dough (66.7 ± 1.1 %) as well as the acidified dough (59.8 ± 0.3 %) exhibited decreased protein solubility compared to the control (72.5 ± 0.1 %). Moreover, emulsion stability, foaming, and gel formation relative to the direct use of FPC were strongly pH dependent. Dough formation and acidification offer a promising strategy for enhancing the potential of plant-based ingredients and pave the way for the development of fermented legume dough-based ingredients.

1. Introduction

Our current food system primarily relies on animal-based food products, which are unsustainable and resource-intensive, leading to the emission of greenhouse gases, inefficient use of arable land, and ethical concerns. Moreover, it accounts for approximately 26 % of total anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions (Poore & Nemecek, 2018). The need to tackle these challenges has motivated the transition to a more plant-based diet, addressing the future demand for alternative protein sources, supporting a healthy lifestyle and protecting the environment (McClements & Grossmann, 2021; Willett et al., 2019). Legumes show great potential as alternative protein source due to their high quality and functionality (Onwezen et al., 2021; van der Weele et al., 2019). A suitable legume with great potential is faba bean (*Vicia faba*), due to its acceptance by consumers, affordability, and its adaptability to different climates (Boukid & Castellari, 2022). Moreover, faba bean has the biological ability for nitrogen fixation and is an excellent source of lysine-rich protein (Dhull et al., 2022). Faba can be consumed whole or

processed into protein-rich ingredients, which come in three forms: flours, concentrates, and isolates. Protein isolates have the highest protein content, followed by concentrates and flours, although isolates retain the least native protein structure, which is associated with reduced ingredient functionality (McClements & Grossmann, 2021). Conventional extraction of protein is performed using wet extraction methods, which result in isolates with high purity but excessive use of energy, water and raw materials (Schutyser et al., 2025). An alternative extraction method is dry fractionation, yielding less pure concentrates, but higher native functional properties, and the use of fewer resources (Schutyser et al., 2015). Off-flavours and antinutritional factors (ANFs), such as lectins, tannins, and phytates are however accumulated in the protein concentrates (Schutyser et al., 2025; Shevkani et al., 2019). To date however, it has been challenging to develop nutritious plant-based foods with sensory properties that meet consumer preferences using dry-fractionated faba bean protein concentrates. Fermentation is one of the oldest food processes that can be used to improve the technical, functional, nutritional, and sensory properties of legume protein

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Fig. 1. Schematic overview of the experimental set-up. Illustration is created in <https://BioRender.com>.

ingredients (Caplice & Fitzgerald, 1999; Paul Ross et al., 2002). Particularly, lactic acid fermentation (LAF) shows great potential for improving the properties of dry fractionated pulse protein ingredients. For instance, the combination of dry fractionation and LAF has been employed to increase the nutritional and technical functionality of chickpea (Xing et al., 2020), pea (Çabuk et al., 2018), and faba bean (Coda et al., 2015). LAF is however a complex process involving effects of the hydration of the ingredient with limited amounts of water (Xing et al., 2020), and a microbial consortium consuming sugars and producing a variety of metabolites. Like in sourdough bread making, during LAF of legumes, sufficient water is added to the ingredient to hydrate their components and make them available for growth and metabolism of lactic acid bacteria, resulting in the formation of a sourdough. Typically, sourdough is applied in breadmaking. In this study, we aim to extend its use beyond bread production and explore its potential for dairy and meat analogues, where gelling and emulsifying properties are essential. During LAF, the microorganisms induce enzymatic reactions, such as proteolysis and the production of exopolysaccharides (EPS), depending on the culture and fermentation conditions, affecting protein structure and interactions with other compounds. Moreover, metabolites to which the texture and shelf life of sourdough bread can be attributed, like organic acids, are produced during LAF (Emkani et al., 2022). This complexity and limited knowledge hinder understanding the effects of LAF on legume proteins in doughs, and thus on the functional properties of protein ingredients processed therewith. Considering that hydration and acidification can change the structural conformation of plant proteins, affecting functional properties, both factors are critical to understand. Literature has for instance shown clear effects of pH on water binding, foaming capacity, and emulsion stability of various plant proteins, while also hydration is known as a critical process in unfolding and functionalising proteins (Akintayo et al., 1999; Aluko & Yada, 1995; Arogundade et al., 2006; Rupley & Careri, 1991). Moreover, their effects on cereal doughs have been reported by

Verdonck et al. (2025b). To pave the way for an increased understanding of the effects of LAF (Coda et al., 2015; Xing et al., 2020; Çabuk et al., 2018), it is hypothesised that dough formation and acidification per se can modify properties of a protein concentrate, altering their application potential in foods. To our knowledge, no previous studies have been performed where faba bean ingredients were functionalized based on acidification and dough formation.

Accordingly, the objective of this study is to elucidate the effects of hydration and acidification, under conditions simulating LAF, on the physicochemical and techno-functional properties of a commercial faba bean protein concentrate (FPC). The study starts with the characterisation of non-acidified and acidified FPC doughs in terms of texture, microstructure and protein structure, followed by characterisation of their colloidal suspensions formed by diluting the doughs at target protein concentration. Functionality of the doughs was assessed in terms of emulsion stability, foaming capacity, and gelation. These results will provide new insights into how fermented plant protein sourdoughs can serve as a functional ingredient for dairy alternatives, in comparison with non-fermented ingredients.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Faba bean (*Vicia faba*) protein concentrate (FPC) produced by dry fractionation was obtained from Vestkorn A/S (Tau, Norway). The protein content of the FPC was determined using the Dumas combustion method and a protein conversion factor of 5.4 (Mariotti et al., 2008). The FPC had a protein content of 50.9 ± 0.1 % w/w and contained 7.7 ± 0.1 % w/w moisture, as determined by drying 1.5 ± 0.5 g for 18 h in a 105 °C convection oven. According to the supplier, the FPC contained 4.5 % w/w fat, 14 % w/w dietary fibre, 10 % w/w carbohydrates, and 6.5 % w/w ash. Ultrapure water was used from a Synergy® water

purification system from Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany). All other chemicals were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA). All experiments were conducted at room temperature.

2.2. Preparation of the doughs and dispersions

Powder-based dispersions with a protein content of 5 % w/w were freshly prepared one day before measurement, by mixing the required amount of FPC with ultrapure water and stirring at 500 rpm at 4 °C for 18 h. For the dough preparation, FPC was mixed with ultrapure water or lactic acid in water (1M) using a Mixolab 2 (Chopin Technologies, Villeneuve-la-Garenne, France) to obtain a dough with a water content of 0.8 g/g_{solids} and a pH of 4.6 for the acidified dough, measured by a pH meter (HI99161, Hanna Instruments, Woonsocket, RI, USA) with a food penetration probe. The pH of the non-acidified dough was 6.4 before incubation, and did not decrease below 6.3 after incubation, not reflecting significant growth of lactic acid bacteria. A dough yield of 160 (dough weight × 100/flour weight) was obtained, similar to a cereal-based sourdough (Curiel et al., 2015). To guarantee full hydration, the dough was transferred to a screw-tight 120 mL PP container to prevent evaporation and incubated at 37 °C for 18 h (VWR, INCU-Line 68R), to mimic conditions during actual LAF. After incubation, the doughs were diluted to a protein content of 5 % w/w to allow screening of the functional properties relevant for plant-based dairy alternatives. The mixture was stirred using an overhead stirrer (RE16, Janke and Kunkel IKA Labortechnik, Denmark) for 1 min at 1500 rpm, followed by scraping with a rubber bowl scraper and high shear mixing using an Ultra Turrax® homogeniser (T25, Janke and Kunkel IKA Labortechnik, Denmark) at 8000 rpm for 5 min until the ingredient was fully dispersed. The pH of the protein dispersions was consequently adjusted to pH 4.4, 6.4, and 7.0 by addition of NaOH or HCl. A pH value of 4.4 was the native pH of the dispersion prepared with the acidified dough, pH 6.4 was the native pH of the dispersions prepared with both FPC and non-acidified dough, and pH 7.0 was chosen as neutral pH, suitable to produce a broad range of food applications. A schematic overview of the experimental set-up can be found in Fig. 1.

2.3. Texture profile analysis (TPA)

Texture analysis of the doughs was performed using a TA.XTplusC texture analyser (Stable Microsystems, UK) with a 5 kg load cell. The container with 16 g of dough was locked in place under an SMSP/0.25S probe and measured directly using the following conditions for measurement: pre-test speed: 5.00 mm/s, test speed: 5.00 mm/s, post-test speed: 10.00 mm/s, target mode: distance, distance: 2.000 mm, trigger type: auto (force), trigger force: 5.0 g. The hardness and adhesiveness of the doughs were analysed using the Exponent Connect software (Stable Microsystems, UK).

2.4. Proton mobility characterisation

Proton mobility after dough incubation was measured using low-field nuclear magnetic resonance (LF-NMR) with an MQR Spectro-P spectrometer (Oxford Instruments, Oxfordshire, UK), operating at a proton resonance frequency of 20.5 MHz (0.47 T). Before measurements, 2g of the sample was transferred into an 18 mm NMR glass tube. All measurements were performed using a Carr-Purcell-Meiboom-Gill (CPMG) pulse sequence. The acquisition parameters were as follows: repetition delay of 4 s, echo time τ of 100 μ s, 64 scans and 8000 echoes. Transverse relaxation time constants T_{2n} and relative proton concentrations M_{2n} were obtained by exponential fitting of the decay curves using an in-house MATLAB script (R2022a, MathWorks, MA, USA), based on the following equation:

$$I(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N M_{2n} \cdot e^{-t/T_{2n}}$$

Where $I(t)$ correspond to the echo intensity with the increasing time, N is the number of proton populations in the sample determined by visual inspection of residuals after fitting, T_{2n} is the transverse relaxation time constant, and M_{2n} is the corresponding relative proton concentration. This analysis was carried out in duplicate.

2.5. Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to investigate structural changes in non-acidified and acidified doughs, freshly prepared and after 18 h of incubation. Three samples were collected from each batch, with three independent batches analysed at room temperature. Spectral acquisition was carried out with a Bruker Vertex 80 spectrometer, equipped with a deuterated-triglycine sulphate (DTGS) detector, a potassium bromide (KBr) beam splitter, and a single reflection Platinum ATR diamond accessory. ATR spectra were recorded in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , with 64 scans co-added per measurement.

2.6. Confocal and Raman microscopy

Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) was used to observe the microstructure of the non-acidified and acidified doughs. The doughs were stained using the bulk water technique, in which part of the dispersant was replaced with a Rhodamine B solution to achieve a concentration of 1 g/1000 g of the bulk water (Lucas et al., 2018). The doughs were then placed in μ -Slide 8 Well Ibidi slides (Ibidi, Munich, Germany) and imaged using a Leica Stellaris 8 confocal microscope (Leica Biosystems, Wetzlar, Germany). For the protein dispersions, 200 μ L of dispersion was loaded in μ -Slide 8 Well Ibidi slides and imaged using a Leica Stellaris 8 confocal microscope. A 543 nm laser was used for the excitation of Rhodamine B, and emissions were collected at 550–640 nm. To visualise protein and starch granules, a Leica Stellaris 8 CRS (Leica Microsystems, Germany) was used with stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) and Second Harmonic Generation (SHG) without the use of fluorescent dyes. A 40 × /1.1 NA water objective was used, with the SRS signal being collected in the forward direction through a water-immersion condenser set to Kohler illumination by tuning the pump beam to stimulate the Raman shift of 1660 cm^{-1} corresponding to the amide I band. SHG of amylopectin was captured in the epi-direction by the 1031.7 nm Stokes beam (Castanha et al., 2023). Representative images were selected for publication.

2.7. Protein solubility

The protein solubility of the ingredients in dispersion was measured in duplicate. The dispersions were transferred into 2 mL Eppendorf tubes and centrifuged at 15000g for 40 min. The nitrogen content of the supernatant was measured with an NRapid Max Exceed Instrument (Elementar, Germany). An N-factor of 5.4 was used to convert nitrogen content to protein content (Mosse, 1990). Protein solubility was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Protein solubility (\%)} = (\text{protein content supernatant}) / (\text{total protein content}) \times 100.$$

2.8. Particle size distribution

The particle size distribution of the protein dispersions was measured using a Mastersizer 3000 instrument (Malvern Instruments, Worcester-shire, UK) with an automated Hydro MV wet cell disperser. The refractive indices of the particles and water were set at 1.45 and 1.33 respectively.

2.9. Apparent viscosity

The viscosity of the protein dispersions was analysed using a Kinexus rheometer (Kinexus Pro KNX 2100, Malvern, UK) equipped with a cylindrical bob (C25 SW1323 SS) and a fixed cup (PC25 S1851 SS) geometry. The cup was loaded with 17.6 mL of dispersion and equilibrated to 25 °C. The shear rate was then increased from 0.1 s⁻¹ to 100 s⁻¹, and after steady state has been automatically detected by the rheometer, the viscosity was measured at increasing shear rates of 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 5.0, 10.0, 50.0, and 100.0 s⁻¹ (Kornet et al., 2022). The shear ramp was used to determine whether the dispersions showed shear-thinning behaviour and to analyse differences in flow properties.

2.10. Accelerated physical stability analysis

The colloidal stability of the protein dispersions was analysed using an analytical centrifuge (LUMiSizer®, LUM GmbH, Berlin, Germany). Freshly prepared samples (400 µL) were transferred into 8 mm × 2 mm rectangular polycarbonate cuvettes and centrifuged at 400 rpm for 2 h, with near-infrared (NIR) light illuminating the samples throughout the analysis, and the intensity of the transmitted light over the length of the sample was measured every 60 s. Results are presented as integral transmission of the NIR light over time.

2.11. Screening of techno-functional properties

For screening the techno-functional properties, the focus was on analysing emulsion stability, foaming capacity, and heat-induced gelation behaviour. All analyses were carried out in duplicate.

Coarse emulsions were prepared by mixing the protein dispersions with rapeseed oil in a ratio of 90:10 in 50 mL Falcon tubes. The samples were then sheared with an Ultra Turrax® homogeniser equipped with an S 10 N-10 G dispersing tool (Janke and Kunkel IKA Labortechnik, Denmark) at 15000 rpm for 2 min. The stability of emulsions was assessed using an analytical centrifuge (LUMiSizer®, LUM GmbH, Berlin, Germany). For analysis, 400 µL of coarse emulsion was transferred into 8 mm × 2 mm rectangular polycarbonate cuvettes and centrifuged at 100g for 15 min (Jaeger et al., 2023).

Foaming capacity was analysed using a Dynamic foam analyser (DFA 100, Kruss, Hamburg, Germany). For analysis, 30 mL of dispersion was added into the equipment glass column and sparged at a 0.3 L/min from the bottom of the column through a 16–40 µm pore size filter (Higa et al., 2025). The maximum foam height was measured through a 30-min run, and foam capacity was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\text{Foaming capacity (\%)} = \text{Max foam vol/vol of gas injected.}$$

To analyse differences in heat-induced gelation behaviour between the ingredients, 1.5 mL of dispersion was transferred to 2 mL Eppendorf tubes and heated to 95 °C for 5 min in a ThermoMixer C (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). The tubes were then put in the fridge at 4 °C and left overnight. The next day, they were inverted to observe gelation.

2.12. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Version 29.0 (IBM Corp., USA). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) with the Tukey post-hoc test ($p < 0.05$) was used to determine significant differences between the samples. Principal component analysis (PCA) was carried out using PLS Toolbox 8.7 (Eigenvector Research, Wenatchee, WA, USA) in MATLAB 2022a environment. All measurements were conducted in triplicate, unless otherwise stated. Figures were made using Origin 2020 (Origin Lab Corporation, USA).

Fig. 2. Images of the freshly prepared non-acidified dough (A) and acidified dough (B). Pictures denoted with a and b represent the non-acidified and acidified dough respectively, after 18 h of incubation at 37 °C.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physicochemical properties of FPC doughs

Characterisation of ingredients is important for the development of food products. Therefore, the initial focus was on characterising and comparing the physicochemical properties of the non-acidified and acidified doughs. The macrostructure, microstructure, and textural properties of the doughs were investigated.

3.1.1. Structural characterisation of FPC doughs

Fig. 2 shows the appearance of the non-acidified dough (A, a) and acidified dough (B, b), freshly prepared (uppercase) and after 18 h incubation at 37 °C (lowercase).

The colour differences of the doughs may be attributed to non-enzymatic and/or enzymatic browning reactions taking place during incubation at 37 °C. Previous studies have shown similar results for dry-heated FPC at elevated temperatures (Bühler et al., 2020) and for faba bean cotyledons stored at 37 °C (Nasar-Abbas et al., 2009). Given the pH of the acidified dough, protonation of amino acid groups may reduce their reactivity, leading to less formation of brown pigments than in the non-acidified dough (Renn & Sathe, 1997). Browning induced by polyphenol oxidases (PPO) could also have resulted in pigment formation in the non-acidified dough at mild temperatures (Friedman, 1996). The optimum pH for most PPO lies between 5.0 and 8.0 (Zhang, 2023). Considering the pH of the non-acidified dough (6.3), the greater extent of browning might be attributed to higher PPO activity.

At equal liquid volume added, the non-acidified dough (A; pH 6.3) appeared wetter and exhibited a less compact, more adhesive texture compared to the acidified dough (B; pH 4.6). The acidified dough (B) showed greater resistance during mixing, as indicated by the Mixolab curves (Fig. S1). After incubation, the colour of the non-acidified dough (a) and acidified dough (b) became darker and more orange. The texture of the acidified dough (b) appeared crumblier and more granulated compared to the non-acidified dough. Texture profile analysis (TPA) was employed for investigating the hardness (g) and adhesiveness (g·s) of the

Fig. 3. Adhesiveness (left) and hardness (right) of the non-acidified (■) and acidified (■) doughs before and after incubation. Distinct letters indicate significant differences among the results of different samples ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 4. Microstructure of the non-acidified dough (A) and acidified dough (B). Images a and b represent the non-acidified and acidified dough respectively, after 18 h of incubation at 37 °C. Images were taken at $\times 10$ magnification.

doughs (Fig. 3). The adhesiveness of the doughs represents the force required to pull the probe away from the sample in grams-seconds, reflecting the stickiness of the sample. The adhesiveness was affected by both acidification and incubation, with the non-acidified dough having a larger adhesiveness compared to the acidified dough, both before and after incubation. The adhesiveness of the non-acidified dough decreased from 34.7 ± 1.7 g s to 24.6 ± 3.4 g s after incubation, while that of the acidified dough increased from 6.2 ± 2.0 g s to 15.7 ± 3.8 g s. The

acidified dough had a hardness value of 329.1 ± 29.2 g compared to 90.8 ± 12.4 g for the non-acidified dough. The hardness of the non-acidified dough did not change after incubation, while the hardness of the acidified dough increased to a value of 421.1 ± 8.4 g.

The differences in textural properties suggest distinct chemical changes among the samples and could be attributed to variations in protein solubility and hydration, possibly even leading to acid-induced gelation, as also seen by an increased hardness after incubation in the

Fig. 5. Representative images of the non-acidified dough (A) and acidified dough (B). Images denoted with a and b represent the non-acidified and acidified dough respectively, after 18 h of incubation at 37 °C. The numbers 1 and 2 represent duplicate representative images of the samples. Images were taken at $\times 40$ magnification. Asrs and Bsrs show the microstructure taken with SRS microscopy.

acidified dough. The acidification caused protein unfolding and aggregation, reducing solubility, leading to decreased adhesiveness and increased hardness (McClements & Grossmann, 2021; Shevkani et al., 2019). The acidification resulted in the formation of a more rigid structure, in line with macroscopic observations, and a significantly lower adhesiveness (Fig. 2B).

The microstructure of the doughs was characterised using CLSM at two different length scales to understand the overall structure of the dough and obtain more details of protein network formation in the matrices. Fig. 4 shows CLSM images of the microstructure of the non-acidified dough (A) and acidified dough (B) before (uppercase) and after incubation (lowercase). The micrographs reveal an amorphous structure, with a protein phase in red, with gas bubbles in black entrapped within the phase (A). The acidified dough exhibits a more disrupted, heterogeneous protein phase with less uniform incorporation of the gas (B). Interestingly, and in contrast to the non-acidified dough, the air was not present as bubbles. After incubation (a, b), no noticeable structural changes were observed for both doughs.

Fig. 5 shows the microstructure of the doughs taken with a $40 \times$ objective, showing more detail of the protein network, including the

presence of small needle-like structures in all samples. These structures are likely cell structures, such as cellulose and hemicellulose, based on the composition of the FPC and observations in work by Coda et al. (2015). In all images, starch granules were identified using stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) imaging (Asrs and Bsrs). Some black circular objects are starch granules with a typical diameter of around $20 \mu\text{m}$, aligning with literature (Vogelsang-O'Dwyer et al., 2020). The SRS images reveal the presence of air, and starch granules in green. Like Fig. 4, the acidified dough exhibits a less cohesive protein network. No major differences were observed resulting from the incubation.

With previous knowledge of wheat dough systems, legume-based products are also known to have the ability to form viscoelastic protein networks (Patil et al., 2020; Shen et al., 2025). Previous studies have shown that decreased pH values of 3.0 in wheat doughs can reduce dough elasticity (Bennett & Ewart, 1962). Moreover, Wehrle et al. (1997) showed that wheat doughs containing acids were firmer and more viscous than doughs without acids, which was also observed in hardness values using TPA. In addition, Seguchi et al. (1997) found a sharp increase in viscosity and water holding capacity of wheat doughs prepared with flours treated with gaseous acetic acid. CLSM images of

Fig. 6. A) Relative proton populations (M_{2n}) for non-acidified dough (M_{21} , M_{22} , M_{23}) and acidified dough (M_{21} , M_{22} , M_{23}) with M_{21} , M_{22} , and M_{23} representing tightly bound water, entrapped water, and mobile water respectively, after 18 h of incubation. B) Relaxation times (T_{2n}) of the non-acidified (\blacktriangledown) and acidified (\bullet) doughs after 18 h of incubation at 37 °C.

the FPC doughs revealed a more disrupted, less cohesive network in the acidified dough, suggesting differences in molecular interactions. Similar observations have been made in acidified maize, soya-enriched, and pea-enriched doughs (Falade et al., 2014; Ronda et al., 2014). There is no universally accepted consensus about the exact molecular interactions of lactic acid in doughs, but it is expected that the hydrogen ions supplied by the organic acid cause protein unfolding, reduced surface charge, and aggregation, which decreases the solubility of the proteins, modifying dough properties. This might explain the differences in microstructure and textural properties between the non-acidified and acidified doughs (Verdonck et al., 2025b). The protein aggregation resulted in the inability of the protein network to stabilise protein-air films, leading to irregular gas incorporation (Figs. 4 and 5). Moreover, the presence of these aggregates, combined with the high tendency of lactic acid to form hydrogen bonds, could potentially lead to the formation of an apparent more dehydrated dough, as also observed for wheat dough constituents (Frandsen et al., 2020; Verdonck et al., 2025a). This suggests that modifications in water holding, induced by acidification, might cause the differences in microstructure and dough textural properties.

3.1.2. Effects of acidification on structure by LF-NMR

Three proton populations with different relaxation times were identified in the doughs, indicating the presence of three distinct structural domains, represented by their relaxation times T_{21} , T_{22} , and T_{23} . T_{21} represents the relaxation times (0–7 ms) of the tightly bound protons with relative proton concentration (M_{21}), which may refer to water bound to macromolecules, like proteins and starches (Assifaoui et al., 2006). T_{22} represents the relaxation times (8–30 ms) of the protons of the immobilised proton population with relative proton concentration (M_{22}), sometimes referred to as entrapped within the matrix of macromolecules, as shown in wheat dough (Raun et al., 1999). The proton population with the highest mobility (T_{23}) exhibits relaxation times in the range 50–120 ms and can be assigned to the water population with the highest molecular mobility (M_{23}).

Fig. 6A shows that in the non-acidified dough, the immobilised water protons entrapped in the macromolecular matrix (M_{22}) have the highest abundance (73.0 ± 3.3 %), whereas in the acidified dough, the water population with the highest abundance (87.5 ± 1.6 %) is the strongly bound population (M_{21}). The least abundant (5.0 ± 0.1 %, non-acidified dough and 2.5 ± 0.3 %, acidified dough) proton population in both doughs is the population of protons with the highest mobility (M_{23}). The differences in structural domains between the non-acidified and

acidified doughs suggest that changes occur because of acidification.

Fig. 6B shows the transverse relaxation times (T_{2n}) representing the proton populations. The non-acidified dough shows lower T_{21} , T_{22} , and T_{23} values compared to the acidified doughs after incubation, indicating a lower mobility of the corresponding proton populations. The proton population with the highest mobility constituted 2.5 ± 0.3 % of the protons of the acidified dough, making up for a minor fraction. These observations, combined with the most abundant proton population being the strongly bound water (M_{21} , 87.5 ± 1.6 %), suggest shifted molecular water binding compared to the non-acidified dough. A potential cause of the differences in water population sizes is that lactic acid can have dimers and hydrogen bonds with the water in the system, contributing to more binding of water on the molecular level (Frandsen et al., 2020). Moreover, the lactic acid likely induces unfolding and aggregation of the proteins, altering their water-binding dynamics in the dough. This is in line with the confocal images in Fig. 4. Interestingly, there is a strong indication of chemical changes. Comparing the transverse relaxation time constants of the non-acidified and acidified doughs, it is noticeable that the values for the acidified dough are higher than those of the non-acidified dough. This suggests a weaker binding force towards hydrogen protons, and thus increased mobility of the proton populations, which is in line with the confocal images (Figs. 4 and 5) revealing a more open network, and with research of Verdonck et al. (2025a).

3.1.3. Changes in protein secondary structure upon incubation and acidification

FTIR spectroscopy was employed to study the effect of incubation and acidification on the protein molecular structure of the FPC doughs. PCA was used to reduce the dimensionality of the spectroscopic data and to highlight subtle variations between samples, enabling visualisation of potential clustering. Fig. 7A shows the FTIR spectra with corresponding peaks. Both doughs displayed typical absorption bands, including bands for Amide I (1600–1700 cm^{-1}) and Amide II (1500–1600 cm^{-1}). Fig. 7B shows the scores (left) and loadings (right) of the first two principal components of the FTIR spectra for all samples in the Amide I (1600–1700 cm^{-1}) and II (1500–1600 cm^{-1}) bands (Rahman et al., 2019). The loadings highlight the wavenumbers that contribute most to differences among samples. The first principal component (PC1) reveals peaks around 1632 cm^{-1} and 1538 cm^{-1} , typically associated with stretching of the amide $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ bond and bending of the $\delta\text{N-H}$ bond respectively (Altan & Yağci, 2023; Shevkani et al., 2019). The second principal component (PC2) reveals peaks in similar regions, indicating a strong

Fig. 7. A) FTIR spectra of the non-acidified and acidified doughs, before and after incubation. Numbers represent corresponding wavenumbers with observed peaks. B) Principal component analysis (PCA) of the FTIR spectra. Left: scores plot of the non-acidified and acidified doughs with 95 % confidence interval. Replicates are presented from freshly prepared non-acidified (ND) and acidified doughs (AD), as well as after incubation (ND_incu, AD_incu). Right: loadings plot of the principal component 1 (PC1) and 2 (PC2). The spectral region between 1200 and 1900 cm⁻¹ is shown.

contribution of the Amide II region. In general, the samples show equal distribution of structural domains, with the most significant spectral shifts occurring in the Amide II region (1600–1500 cm⁻¹). The scores plot shows clear clustering of the samples according to their processing, grouping the non-acidified dough before incubation, after incubation, and the acidified dough.

A distinction can be seen between the non-acidified and acidified doughs, with clear grouping over PC1. The samples cluster less over PC2, contributing only minor spectral variations. The differences between the samples are well captured in the scores plot, showing that PC1, explaining 83.03 % of the total variance, explains differences in acidification, whereas PC2, explaining 13.99 % of the variance, likely captures the effects of incubation and/or hydration. The changes in secondary structure can be explained by looking at the wavenumber shifts. Particularly, the shift around 1550 cm⁻¹ suggests that β -forms (1633 cm⁻¹) shift to more protein aggregation (Carbonaro et al., 2008). PCA revealed that incubation or hydration only mildly influenced the

secondary structure of the non-acidified doughs. This could potentially be attributed to the growth of autochthonous microorganisms, possibly exerting proteolysis, leading to structural changes, although no indications for microbial growth were observed. Separation along PC2 is not observed for the acidified dough, with the acidification acting as a preservative, inhibiting microbial growth. Moreover, the acidification likely affects the molecular structure of the protein, as shown by shifts around 1633 cm⁻¹ in the Amide II region, suggesting a loss or reorganisation of protein secondary structure (Jeganathan et al., 2024). These results suggest that the hydrogen bonds were disrupted by acidification, causing partial protein unfolding. Moreover, the film-forming capacity of the proteins was inhibited, suggesting altered protein structure. These results are in line with CLSM images, confirming that acidification exerts dominant effects on the protein structure, likely affecting techno-functionality of the dough in terms of gelation and emulsifying properties.

Fig. 8. Protein solubility of dispersions prepared with FPC powder (■), non-acidified dough (■), and acidified dough (■) at pH 4.4, 6.4, and 7.0. Distinct letters indicate significant differences among the results of different samples ($p < 0.05$).

3.2. Properties of protein dispersions from FPC doughs

Dispersing ingredients in an aqueous system at a defined protein content is a standard step in the processing of plant-based dairy and meat alternatives. Therefore, 5 % protein dispersions prepared with FPC powder, non-acidified dough, and acidified dough were compared to understand the impact of dough formation and acidification on the physicochemical and technological properties of the dispersions at pH 4.4, 6.4, and 7.0. The preparation of the dispersion by direct use of FPC powder reflects common industrial practice. The physicochemical and technological properties evaluated included protein solubility, particle size distribution, shear viscosity, and accelerated stability of the dispersions.

3.2.1. Protein solubility

Fig. 8 shows the protein solubility of the dispersions at pH 4.4, 6.4, and 7.0 prepared with the FPC powder, non-acidified dough, and acidified dough. At pH 4.4, no significant differences were observed, with solubilities ranging from 9.7 ± 0.3 % to 10.6 ± 0.3 % w/w. All samples showed higher protein solubilities under neutral conditions ($p < 0.05$). The protein solubility of the dispersions at pH 6.4 and 7.0 showed a similar trend, with the powder dispersion having the highest protein solubility of 71.1 ± 0.7 % w/w and 72.5 ± 0.1 % w/w respectively,

followed by the non-acidified dough dispersion with values of 64.3 ± 0.6 % w/w at pH 6.4 and 66.7 ± 0.7 % w/w at pH 7.0, and the acidified dough dispersion with protein solubilities of 47.0 ± 2.7 % and 59.8 ± 0.4 % at pH 6.4 and 7.0 respectively.

Protein solubility is influenced by the pH, particularly close to the isoelectric point, where the surface charge of the proteins is minimal, leading to an increase in aggregation (McClements & Grossmann, 2021). Denaturation and unfolding of the protein at pH 4.4 could have led to aggregation. These aggregates sediment during the centrifugation step and result in decreased protein solubility. This aligns with the broader particle size distributions of the dispersions at pH 4.4 (Fig. 9). On the other hand, hydration allows interactions with water molecules, solubilising the components, hypothesising an increased protein solubility, which is not observed for the doughs. At pH 6.4 and 7.0, further away from the isoelectric point of the FPC protein (pH 4.1), a decreased protein surface charge caused more repulsion, and therefore less protein aggregation, resulting in higher protein solubilities. Fig. 8 further shows lower protein solubilities in the non-acidified and acidified dough dispersions compared to the powder-based dispersion. In research by Çabuk et al. (2018), a comparable trend was observed, with decreased protein solubility of a pea protein-enriched flour after LAF, attributed to acidification. Similarly, a possible explanation is that lactic acid induced irreversible protein coagulation, and thus a decrease in protein solubility, even at pH values further from the isoelectric point. Similar phenomena have been shown in literature before (Emkani et al., 2022; Schlegel et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2019). This confirms the findings in Fig. 6, revealing a large population of tightly bound protons, possibly indicating the ability of the insoluble aggregates in the acidified dough to bind water.

3.2.2. Particle size distributions

The volume-weighted particle size distributions (PSD) of the protein dispersions formed with FPC powder, non-acidified, and acidified dough at pH 4.4, 6.4, and 7.0 are displayed in Fig. 9. All dispersions, except the non-acidified dough at pH 6.4, show a monomodal size distribution. The dispersions exhibit a dominant peak in the range of 2–100 μm , centred around 20 μm , similar to what has been reported for various faba bean-based ingredients (Li et al., 2024; Vogelsang-O'Dwyer et al., 2020). At pH 4.4, the acidified dough dispersion exhibits the narrowest size distribution compared to the powder and non-acidified dough dispersions. Increasing the pH shows an increase in volume density of the dominant peak in the range of 2–100 μm , with the peak shoulders that can be observed at pH 4.4 getting incorporated into the dominant peak, indicating a more uniform size distribution under neutral conditions.

At present, protein-rich legume ingredients are used in powdered form for food formulation. However, protein powders, especially those obtained by dry fractionation, require extended rehydration times to

Fig. 9. Representative volume weighted particle size distributions of FPC dispersions with 5 % w/w protein, formed with FPC powder (—), non-acidified (—), and acidified dough (—). The figure shows volume density (%) over the size classes (μm) at the three pH values analysed.

Fig. 10. Shear viscosity of protein dispersions prepared with FPC powder (■), non-acidified dough (●), and acidified dough (▲) at pH 4.4, 6.4, and 7.0 as a function of shear rate. Data points are shown at shear rates of 5, 10, 50, and 100 s^{-1} .

achieve optimal protein functionality. Using these ingredients in dough form is a novel and previously unexplored approach that offers improved functionality due to pre-rehydration. The particle size distributions are similar to the control condition, as well as to what has been previously reported in literature for dispersing plant protein concentrates in powder form (Li et al., 2024). By reducing the pH, the volume density of large particles in the powder and non-acidified dough dispersions decreases. In contrast, the acidified dough exhibits the narrowest size distribution at pH 4.4, suggesting the most uniform size distribution. Extensive aggregation may have caused this, with aggregates of this size dominating the dispersion, while for the other conditions, differently sized aggregates might still be present because of less acid-induced denaturation. At pH 6.4, a small peak is observed in the range of 0.4–1.0 μm for the non-acidified dough, possibly attributed to bacterial growth. The non-acidified dough was incubated without lactic acid, potentially allowing growth of autochthonous bacteria. This small peak was not observed for the acidified dough, and similar to LAF being considered a bio-preservation method, the reduced pH in this mimic may have inhibited the growth of spoiling bacteria (Emkani et al., 2022). The control condition was hydrated at 4 °C, explaining the absence of this minor peak. Arguing that the minor peak should be visible at the other pH values analysed as well, another possible explanation is that exposure of the dough to moderate temperatures might have caused disintegration of the aggregates formed upon dough formation, showing a minor peak in the size distribution at pH 6.4, which is the native pH of the non-acidified dough dispersion. Adjusting the pH may have caused these to aggregate again and incorporate into the dominant peak in the distribution.

3.2.3. Shear viscosity

Fig. 10 shows the shear viscosities of the different dispersions over a shear rate of 1–100 s^{-1} at pH 4.4, 6.4, and 7.0. All samples showed the highest viscosity at low shear rates, followed by a decrease in viscosity for increasing shear rates, indicating shear-thinning behaviour of all samples. At pH 4.4, the viscosities of the three ingredients lie close to each other. While at pH 6.4, the viscosity of the dispersion prepared with acidified dough is significantly higher compared to the dispersion prepared with powder and non-acidified dough ($p < 0.05$). At pH 7.0, the viscosities show no significant differences again, while also showing less shear-thinning compared to the measurements at pH 4.4.

Shear-thinning could indicate alignment of the particles with shear flow or breakdown of agglomerates present in the sample (Brown et al., 2025). As the proteins have reduced solubility at pH 4.4 (Fig. 8), aggregation and network formation likely occurred, explaining the higher viscosity of the dispersions. Breakdown of these aggregates could cause stronger shear-thinning at higher shear rates compared to the analysis performed at pH 6.4 and 7.0. At pH 6.4, a significantly higher apparent viscosity is observed for the acidified dough dispersion. As the proteins were acidified during incubation of the dough, preformed aggregates might have been present after homogenising, resulting in higher viscosities and more pronounced shear-thinning. Conversely, at pH 7.0, potential repulsion between the proteins made them stay in solution and therefore shows a lower viscosity of the dispersions (McClements & Grossmann, 2021). The dispersions behave more like a Newtonian fluid, showing little change in viscosity with shear. The results indicate the importance of pH and processing history for flow behaviour of FPC doughs in dispersion.

Fig. 11. Accelerated physical stability profiles of the powder-based (■), non-acidified dough-based (●), and acidified dough-based (▲) dispersions, expressed as integral transmission of NIR light over time. Profiles are shown every 180 s of measurement.

Fig. 12. Transmission profiles of the coarse emulsions prepared using powder (FPC), non-acidified dough (ND), and acidified dough (AD) under accelerated gravitation for 15 min. The left-hand side of the profiles represents the top and the right-hand side the bottom of the cuvettes.

3.2.4. Accelerated physical stability

The physical stability was evaluated using an analytical centrifuge to measure the light transmission through the protein dispersions during centrifugation. The stability was expressed as the integrated transmission-time profiles (Fig. 11). A high integral transmission means a low physical stability. At the start of the measurements at all pH values, the dispersions were not destabilised. Little light was transmitted at any point in the cuvette, showing initial transmission values ranging from 7.3 to 12.7 % for the powder dispersion, 7.9–11.2 % for the non-acidified dough dispersion, and 6.5–9.4 % for the acidified dough dispersion. As the protein dispersions were centrifuged, the top of the cuvettes became increasingly transparent, measured as an increase in integral transmission over time. At pH 4.4, instant destabilisation of all samples can be observed upon low centrifugal forces, as the integral light transmission increases quickly. After 7500s of centrifugation, the acidified dough dispersion reaches the highest integral transmission of 48.6 %, compared to 44.1 % and 46.6 % for the powder and non-acidified dough dispersions, respectively. At pH 6.4, the acidified dough dispersion showed the quickest increase in integral transmission. Interestingly, the samples do not show statistically significant differences in integral transmission profiles at pH 7.0 after 7500s of centrifugation, reaching integral transmission values of 17.1 % for the powder, 13.3 % for the non-acidified dough, and 17.6 % for the acidified dough.

As expected, all samples showed the lowest physical stability at pH 4.4, which is close to the isoelectric point of the FPC, causing aggregation of proteins and therefore accelerated sedimentation (McClements & Grossmann, 2021). At pH 6.4, the powder and non-acidified dough dispersions show a significantly higher stability compared to the

acidified dough dispersion, which shows a steep increase in integral transmission over measurement time. The physical stability agrees with the viscosity measurements (Fig. 10). Additionally, this is in line with the results regarding protein solubility and proton mobility, indicating the lowest protein solubility at pH 6.4 and the largest proportion of strongly bound water for the acidified dough, suggesting network formation. The hypothesis that protein aggregates were formed during incubation of the acidified doughs is supported by the micrographs (Fig. S2), revealing the presence of larger aggregates at pH 6.4, which might explain the differences in stability. At pH 7.0, all dispersions show a significantly higher stability compared to pH 4.4. Moreover, the acidified dough dispersion shows a higher stability at pH 7.0 compared to its stability at pH 6.4, which may be attributed to more stability against particle aggregation. These results are in line with Fig. 8 in section 2.7, suggesting a critical minimal protein solubility for physical stability, around 50 %, showing increased stability of the dispersions at pH 7.0. These findings provide insights into the effects of proteins and polysaccharides present in the samples and the possible network structure on the colloidal stability of the systems.

3.3. Screening of techno-functional properties of doughs

It is important to screen the functional properties of the ingredients. Emulsification, gelation, and foaming are crucial functionalities required in the formulation of plant-based applications (McClements & Grossmann, 2021). Investigating these will allow understanding the effects of acidification as a tool for preparing plant-based foods.

Fig. 13. Foaming capacity of dispersions prepared with FPC powder (■), non-acidified dough (■), and acidified dough (■) at pH 4.4, 6.4, and 7.0. No significant differences were found among the results of different samples ($p < 0.05$).

3.3.1. Emulsion stability

Fig. 12 shows the transmission profiles of the oil-in-water emulsions. An increase in transmission on the left side of the profile indicates creaming, while an increase on the right side suggests sedimentation. At pH 4.4 and 7.0, all profiles appeared similar. At pH 6.4, both the powder (a) and non-acidified dough emulsions (b) appeared similar, whereas the acidified dough emulsion (c) showed destabilisation, evidenced by a profile shift. At pH 7.0, all emulsions appeared stable under the measurement conditions.

At pH 4.4, the increase in light transmission for all samples suggests clarification. This typical clarification process was supported by viscosity measurements (Fig. 10). This aligns with literature on fermented pea-protein-enriched flour and soy protein isolate, showing decreased emulsification at acidic pH values, due to changes in conformation, solubility, and hydrophobicity (Emkani et al., 2022; Çabuk et al., 2018). At pH 6.4, only the emulsion prepared with the acidified dough exhibited clarification. Measurements on stability and viscosity of the dispersions also showed differences for the acidified dough at this pH, having lower protein solubility and higher viscosity, suggesting coagulation.

3.3.2. Foaming capacity

Fig. 13 shows the foaming capacity of the FPC dispersion. The powder-based dispersion has the highest foaming capacity at all three pH values analysed, followed by the non-acidified dough at pH 4.4, and the acidified dough at pH 6.4 and 7.0, respectively.

The foaming capacities were not significantly different between the samples. The foam-forming properties of the ingredients depend on the ability of the proteins to migrate to the air-water interface to lower surface tension and stabilise the film, which seems not to be affected by dough formation and acidification in this screening experiment. Literature has reported decreased foaming capacities for fermented legumes, likely caused by hydrolysis during fermentation (Xing et al., 2020; Çabuk et al., 2018). Acidification seems to mainly play a role in protein unfolding, possibly favouring enzymatic activity, although no proteolysis is expected to have taken place in the FPC doughs.

3.3.3. Thermogelation behaviour

The heat-induced gels of the protein dispersions can be seen in Fig. 14. For the powder-based (A) and non-acidified dough-based dispersions (B), self-supporting gels were formed at pH 4.4 and pH 7.0. The acidified dough-based dispersions (C) formed self-supporting gels at all pH values analysed.

Acidification caused reduced electrostatic repulsion of the proteins, enhancing aggregation, and increasing the protein's ability to form gels (McClements & Grossmann, 2021). This is in line with observations in section 3.1, in which the acidified dough clearly showed modifications in protein structural properties. Moreover, the powder-based dispersions (A) and the non-acidified dough-based dispersions (B) show clear differences in gelation ability at pH 6.4, when compared to the gels formed after heating the acidified dough-based dispersion. These observations indicate effects of acidification and incubation on the gelation properties that should be further studied to better understand the role of faba protein ingredient rehydration and solubility on gelation properties.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrated that dough formation and lactic-acid-induced acidification substantially modify the physicochemical properties of faba bean protein concentrate (FPC) and that these structural changes directly shape its techno-functional behaviour after redispersion. Acidification disrupted the dough's protein network, modify water distribution (tightly bound protons: $87.5\% \pm 1.6\%$ vs. $22.0\% \pm 3.2\%$), and produced a markedly firmer dough (421.1 ± 8.4 g vs. 106.3 ± 8.6 g). These modifications translated into protein modifications and increased protein aggregation, reflected by reduced solubility at pH 7.0 ($59.8\% \pm 0.3\%$ vs. $72.5\% \pm 0.1\%$ for control).

In terms of techno-functionality, the dough network promoted stronger gel formation upon heating, indicating that acid-induced aggregation creates protein structures more prone to network reformation. Conversely, the same aggregation reduced surface activity, leading to weaker emulsion stability and poor foaming capacity, particularly at pH 6.4, because rigid protein aggregates are less able to adsorb at interfaces.

Overall, the results show a clear structure–function relationship: acidification reshapes the dough matrix enhancing gelling performance

Fig. 14. Heat-induced gels of FPC powder (A), non-acidified dough (B), and acidified dough-based (C) protein dispersions at a protein content of 5 % w/w. Each image represents the sample at pH 4.4, 6.4, and 7.0 from left to right.

but compromise interfacial properties. This provides a targeted strategy to tailor FPC functionality for plant-based dairy and meat applications where gelation properties are of primary importance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Youp van der Graaf: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tomasz Pawel Czaja:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **José Bonilla:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology. **Lilia Ahrné:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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